

Alcohol Consumption Across Income Groups: How Do Consumers Respond to Price Changes?

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Abstract

In recent decades, Russia has pursued an active anti-alcohol policy. This includes setting a minimum price for alcohol and raising excise duties. However, since 2017, the effectiveness of these measures has declined, while total alcohol consumption has increased. This paper analyses how people with different income levels respond to changes in the price of alcoholic beverages. Using data from the Russian Longitudinal Monitoring Survey–HSE (RLMS) and Rosstat from 2011 to 2022, we examined the alcohol consumption behaviours of different income groups. Two-step Heckman models and instrumental variables were used to calculate the price elasticity of vodka, beer and dry wine consumption in groups with different income levels. The study found that the response to changes in prices of vodka, beer and wine varies greatly between the wealthiest and least wealthy consumer groups. Those with the lowest incomes demonstrate the lowest elasticity of vodka consumption (from -0.123 to -0.196 depending on the number of groups considered) and the highest price elasticity of wine consumption (from -1.41 to -1.52). Conversely, high-income consumers are the most sensitive to increases in vodka prices (consumption elasticity from -0.235 to -0.273) and the least sensitive to increases in wine prices (from -0.618 to -0.694).

Keywords

anti-alcohol policy, income groups, alcohol consumption, price elasticity of consumption, Heckman model

JEL codes: E62, E64, I18, H24

Introduction

Excessive alcohol consumption is still a major social and economic problem in many countries, particularly in highly developed ones. This is due to the adverse consequences for public health and the high economic costs to the state, including loss of human capital. In 2018, approximately 196,000 people in Russia died prematurely from causes related to alcohol consumption (Kuznetsova 2020). The economic losses resulting from alcohol consumption amount to nearly 2% of the country's GDP (Koshkina et al. 2010).

Over the past few decades, Russia has achieved a significant reduction in alcohol consumption, from 14.8 litres of pure alcohol per capita among people over the age of 15 in 2005, to 10.5 litres in 2022¹. However, it still ranks among the countries with the highest alcohol-related mortality rates (WHO 2024).

Pricing mechanisms, such as setting minimum prices and introducing excise duties on alcoholic products, are considered to be one of the most effective tools for reducing alcohol consumption (WHO 2020; WHO 2024; WHO 2025). These measures are also used in Russia, but their effectiveness has declined since 2014: alcohol is becoming more affordable, and the amount of vodka or beer that can be bought on an average wage is increasing year on year (Kolosnitsyna 2024). From 2017 to 2023, sales of alcoholic beverages in terms of pure alcohol have steadily increased from 7.2 to 7.8 litres per adult². However, average indicators of alcohol consumption and the evolution of sales may mask different trends that are specific to certain population groups. For example, people's responses to changes in the price of alcohol may vary depending on factors such as their income level. This has important implications for government policy on regulating alcohol consumption (Kumar 2017; Pryce et al. 2019).

Therefore, it is important to study the price elasticity of demand for alcohol among different income groups in Russia in order to adjust anti-alcohol policy measures, given their declining effectiveness. This study aims to determine the impact of price changes for specific alcoholic beverages (such as vodka, beer and wine) on their consumption among different income groups in Russia.

The impact of prices on alcohol consumption: a review of research

Various models reflect the specific nature of alcohol as an addictive good in theoretical studies of alcohol consumption, as well as its impact on health (i.e. negative investment in human capital) and its marginal utility for consumers in both the short and long term. Key contributions in this literature include Grossman (1972), Becker and Murphy (1988), Becker et al. (1994), and Cook and Moore (2000).

To date, an extensive body of empirical research has been carried out to study alcohol consumption and types of alcohol behaviour, as well as to evaluate public policy instruments. Depending on the focus of each study, authors either review the literature or conduct their own analysis (Bentzen 1999; Pierani and Tiezzi 2004; Yakovlev 2018) with a view

1 According to data from the World Health Organization (WHO). URL: <https://data.who.int/ru/indicators/i/EF38E6A/EE6F72A> (accessed 15 June 2025). This data includes an estimate of unreported consumption.

2 Authors' calculations based on Rosstat data.

to selecting the consumption model to be considered. Many studies have confirmed that price-based public policy instruments, such as introduction or increase of minimum prices or excise duties on alcohol, have the greatest effect in curbing consumption growth (Kolosnitsyna et al. 2015; Subramanian and Kumar 2017; WHO 2025). To confirm the effect of such measures, the elasticity of demand for alcoholic beverages with respect to their own price is usually estimated. This reflects the impact of government-imposed excise duties and/or minimum prices on alcoholic beverages.

Recent studies that have used meta-analysis techniques to estimate the average price elasticity of demand for alcoholic beverages in grams of pure alcohol, based on data from different countries, years and samples, have found it to be around -0.5 (Fogarty 2006; Gallet 2007; Wagenaar et al. 2009; Nelson 2013; Sornpaisarn 2013). Here, we will focus on some studies not included in these reviews that used non-standard estimation methods.

J. Sousa (2014) estimated the consumption elasticities of different types of alcoholic beverages in the United Kingdom. He used a generalised Heckman model with instrumental variables included in the participation equation (i.e. a person's decision to consume alcohol or not). Dummy variables for consumption of other types of alcohol and pork consumption within households were employed as instruments to address the primary reasons for abstaining from alcohol: cultural or personal preferences and religious commitments. All the estimated consumption elasticities of alcoholic beverages with respect to their own prices were significant and negative.

Rousselière (2022) used the Heckman model with country-level bootstrapping based on European data. A distinctive feature of this study is its solution to the problems of aggregation and selection bias that arise when estimating elasticity using macroeconomic data (Nelson 2013; Nelson 2014). In their microdata-based model of individual behaviour, the authors add GDP per capita as a control variable for unobservable country effects. Different values of the direct and cross-elasticity of consumption are found for different beverages, with the consumption of beer and wine proving to be the least elastic.

The opposite result for beer was obtained by Swedish researchers Gruenewald et al. (2006), who found that beer demand was most elastic with respect to its own price. This work is also interesting because the authors used the SURE models³ with beverages divided by quality (from low to high) to find that higher prices for high-quality beverages led to an increase in sales of lower-quality beverages. However, regarding beer consumption, it was noted that, when the price of lower-quality beer increased, sales of cheaper beverages did not rise; in fact, sales of higher-quality beer increased.

Turning to Russian studies, we note that Andrienko and Nemtsov (2005) attempted to estimate elasticity within the context of 'short-sighted' versus rational behaviour models. They found no significant differences in the estimates for these models. The findings for different beverages illustrate the classic negative relationship between demand and price. Price elasticity of consumption varies from -1.0 for wine and -1.8 for vodka to -3.0 for beer.

Around the same time, Baltagi and Geishecker (2006) analysed the rational alcohol-related behaviour in Russia. This study included past and future consumption volumes, as well as past prices, as instrumental variables in the model. The findings revealed that Russian women did not exhibit rational alcohol consumption behaviour, while estimation of the average short- and long-term price elasticity of demand produced ambiguous results across

³ The seemingly unrelated regression model uses a generalised least squares method to estimate a system of equations, assuming that errors for different subjects at the same points in time are correlated.

different models. The authors concluded that the price elasticity of alcohol consumption among men and women was statistically insignificant.

Kolosnitsyna and Sukhanova (2023) and Yakovlev (2018) used a regression structural break model to estimate the impact of the excise duty increase policy introduced after 2011 on demand, in order to estimate the price elasticity of alcohol consumption. Yakovlev found that, in a ‘rational’ consumption model, consumers demonstrated higher price elasticity than in the ‘short-sighted’ model. To illustrate this, the author estimated the impact of government policy – specifically, a sharp increase in excise duties – on demand among heavy drinkers and the mortality rate among men. According to the ‘short-sighted’ model, own-price elasticity implies a decrease in the proportion of heavy drinkers of around 4.5 percentage points when prices increase by 1%. In the ‘clear-sighted’ consumer model, the effect of a price change was approximately 1.35 percentage points higher.

Kolosnitsyna and Sukhanova (2023) used a combination of regression breakpoint, fixed effects and Arellano-Bond estimates to demonstrate that a 1% increase in vodka prices resulted in a 0.5–0.93% reduction in pure alcohol consumption. They showed that the 2011–2014 pricing measures were effective in reducing vodka and overall alcohol consumption. Earlier periods were analysed by M. Kolosnitsyna, N. Khorkina and H. Dorzhiev (2015), who determined that the price elasticity of vodka consumption was equal to -0.01.

However, it is important to note that the average price elasticity of alcohol consumption in grams of pure alcohol provides little information about the effect of pricing policy on individual consumers or the consumption of specific beverages. Firstly, people with different income levels may respond differently to price increases. In Russia, for instance, the highest average consumption of spirits is observed precisely among low-income groups (Roshchina 2012; Odinokova 2014). Statistically, it has been shown that as income levels rise, alcohol consumption decreases. This result was obtained, for example, in studies based on data from Malaysia and Cambodia (Cheah 2015; Chea 2020). Accordingly, given that alcohol is addictive and habit-forming, low-income groups may find it difficult to stop consuming it. Heaviest-drinker groups are likely to have low price elasticity of demand (Pryce et al. 2019), meaning that the proportion of income spent on alcohol may increase as the price rises (Subramanian and Kumar 2017). For instance, Shrestha (2015), based on US data, divided drinkers into quantiles according to their consumption levels. He demonstrated that the heavier drinkers feature low (though not zero) price elasticity of consumption. Therefore, in conditions of severe budget constraints, alcohol expenditure in low-income households incurs significant opportunity costs, as these families would either forego other essential goods or switch to cheaper, lower-quality alternatives when prices rise.

Conversely, if we assume that the price elasticity of alcohol consumption among the poorest groups is relatively high, as was found in a tobacco study in India (Selvaraj et al. 2015), then pricing measures would have the greatest impact on these groups (Mäkelä et al. 2015; Jiang et al. 2016). For instance, a study in India found that setting a minimum price for alcohol had a greater absolute effect on low-income social groups because heavy drinkers on low incomes were more likely to purchase products below the threshold price (Kumar 2017).

It should be emphasised that responses to changes in prices of specific alcoholic beverages may differ even within a population group with the same income level. Goryakin et al. (2015) demonstrated that vodka consumption among low-income Russians increased in line with rising prices, suggesting that vodka may be a Giffen good. The own-price elas-

ticity of consumption of cheap table wine is significant and negative for poorer population segments. Among groups with higher socio-economic status and income, beer is a substitute for table wine. Among wealthier groups, high vodka prices and fortified wine consumption are negatively correlated.

In turn, sociological studies confirm the existence of certain established types of alcohol consumption behaviour in Russia, depending on various social factors (Roshchina and Martynenko 2014; Kondratenko and Roshchina 2021). For instance, beer is the most popular beverage among groups with a relatively low per capita income. As income increases, so does the proportion of people who drink brandy, whisky, wine, and other more expensive beverages. Consequently, the impact of price changes on the consumption of different alcoholic beverages among these groups may vary depending on established preferences.

Data and descriptive analysis

This study used a database of individual and household surveys, Russian Longitudinal Monitoring Survey–HSE (RLMS) conducted by the National Research University Higher School of Economics⁴ from 2011 to 2022 (2011 was chosen as the base year because the most active pricing measures of the anti-alcohol policy began to be implemented in that year; the latest infrastructure and price data available at the time of writing was from 2022). Rosstat data on the socio-economic characteristics of the regions where respondents live and data on the permitted hours for selling alcoholic beverages in these regions, provided by regional authorities, were also used. This was panel data. As the study looked at adult respondents aged 18 to 80 who had participated in at least one survey during the selected period, the sample is unbalanced. Given the panel nature of the sample, the total number of observations, including both consumers and non-consumers of alcohol, amounted to 134,984 for all years. The number of unique units (people included in the sample at least once during the entire period) was 26,360, with the number of respondents varying from approximately 10 thousand to approximately 13 thousand per year.

During the study, the sample was divided into groups based on their income levels. Income was measured using the real average per capita household income in 2011 prices, calculated based on the regional consumer price indices. To calculate this, the highest response value was taken as the total household income from:

- the RLMS household database, responding to the question: ‘What was your family’s total monetary income over the last 30 days? This should include all money received by all family members, including foreign currency, which should be converted into Russian roubles.’
- the database of individual surveys, responding to the question: ‘How much money have you received from your primary employer after taxes over the last 30 days? If you received any of this money in a foreign currency, please convert it all into Russian roubles and report the total amount.’

⁴ Russian Longitudinal Monitoring Survey–HSE (RLMS) conducted by the National Research University Higher School of Economics and OOO Demoscope with participation of the Carolina Population Center at the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill and the Institute of Sociology, Federal Research Centre for Sociology, Russian Academy of Sciences (See RLMS HSE websites at: <http://www.hse.ru/rllms> and <https://rllms-hse.cpc.unc.edu>).

To accurately calculate the average per capita income of a family, the impact of cohabitation within the household was considered using the modified Oxford scale (Ovcharova et al. 2014). According to this scale, the first adult in the household is assigned a weight of ‘1’, each additional person aged 14 and above is assigned a weight of ‘0.5’, and each child under the age of 14 is assigned a weight of ‘0.3’. Outliers were then removed from the initial sample: the 5% of respondents with the lowest and highest incomes.

Within each year, respondents were divided into five groups according to their real per capita income in 2011 prices. The first quintile (group 1) represented the poorest fifth of respondents (up to 20% of those surveyed each year); the second quintile (group 2) represented the next fifth (21% to 40%); and so on. The fifth quintile (group 5) represented the richest fifth (81% to 100%). Each respondent was assigned a value corresponding to their group (from 1 to 5) in each year. As their income varied, they could be in a different group in different years.

Socio-economic characteristics of respondents in different income groups

Table 1 shows the average per capita household income (in roubles, at 2011 prices) and the average age of respondents within each income group throughout the observation period. The average age of respondents in the presented groups is approximately the same, ranging from 44 to 48 years. The decrease in age in groups 4 and 5 is due to two factors. Firstly, peak income levels are reached at 35–40 years of age. Secondly, the presence of children under 14 years in the household increases the average income compared to older children due to the use of the income equivalence scale.

Table 1. Average values for respondents’ age and income by income groups, 2011–2022

Income Groups	Average per capita household income, roubles in 2011 prices	Minimum per capita household income, roubles in 2011 prices	Maximum per capita household income, roubles in 2011 prices	Average age, years
1	7245.616	3248.45	11500.95	45
2	11390.51	8587.29	15283.66	48
3	14818.71	11645.83	19022.41	46
4	19201.21	15005.58	24128.02	45
5	31095.23	19969.35	83611.77	44

Source: authors’ calculations based on RLMS data.

Let us consider the characteristics of alcohol consumption among different income groups. Firstly, we analyse three main types of beverages: vodka, beer, and wine. According to RLMS data, these beverages account for approximately 87% of the total volume of alcohol consumed annually, meaning that statistically significant results cannot be obtained for other beverages such as brandy, whisky, home-made alcohol or cocktails. For the purpose of this analysis, wine consumers are defined as all individuals who have consumed fortified, home-made, dry or sparkling wine in the last 30 days. Outliers in the consumption volumes of each alcoholic beverage were removed separately for the analysis of consumption (for example, those who were removed as outliers in the wine consumer sample may

remain in the vodka consumer sample). Box-and-whisker plots were constructed for each beverage to clean the data of outliers (see Appendix 1, Figure A1). Analysis of the resulting diagrams revealed threshold values for each beverage common to all periods: the values closest to the upper limit of the ‘whiskers’. For the vodka consumption analysis, for example, values above 4.000 grams per month were removed. Consequently, 952 observations were removed, accounting for 1.46% of the total vodka consumption observations and 0.71% of the total observations in the entire sample. For the beer consumption analysis, values above 12.000 grams per month were removed. Accordingly, 2.063 observations were removed, accounting for 3.45% of the total beer consumption observations and 1.53% of the total observations in the entire sample. For wine consumption, values above 5.000 grams per month were removed (563 observations), accounting for 0.61% of the total wine consumption observations and 0.47% of the total sample observations. In total, 3.528 observations were removed, accounting for 2.9% of the entire sample. The outliers were distributed relatively evenly across the five income groups of respondents for all beverages considered, without any bias.

Figure 1 shows the proportion of people in income quintiles who consume alcohol at least occasionally⁵. Whereas around 57% of people in the low-income groups consume alcohol, this figure rises to 66% in group 5, indicating a clear gap in the prevalence of alcohol consumption.

Figure 1. Percentage of people who consume alcoholic beverages, including beer, at least occasionally, by income group. *Source:* authors’ calculations based on RLMS data.

Figures 2–4 show the evolution of the proportion of respondents who consumed vodka, beer or wine in the last 30 days among those who consume alcohol at least occasionally. Fig-

⁵ In our study, people who responded that they consume alcohol at least occasionally will be considered ‘consumers.’

Figure 2 shows that, in 2011, around 50% of alcohol consumers in all income groups consumed vodka. Between 2011 and 2022, the proportion of vodka consumers declined, with the rate of decline accelerating with increasing income: the proportion fell by 16.04% in group 1, 17.57% in group 2, 18.42% in group 3, 18.43% in group 4 and 22.64% in group 5.

Figure 2. Proportion of people who have consumed vodka in the last 30 days, among those who consume alcohol at least occasionally, by income group (%). *Source:* authors’ calculations based on RLMS data.

Figure 3. Proportion of people who have consumed beer in the last 30 days among those who consume alcoholic beverages at least occasionally, by income group (%). *Source:* authors’ calculations based on RLMS data.

Figure 4. Proportion of people who have consumed wine in the last 30 days among those who consume alcoholic beverages at least occasionally, by income group, %. *Source:* authors' calculations based on RLMS data.

Beer consumption trends differed significantly during the same period (see Fig. 3). Between 2011 and 2022, the proportion of people who consumed beer among alcohol consumers increased in all groups, but at different rates: faster in the three least affluent groups (by around 7%), and slower in the relatively wealthy groups (by 2–3%).

Now let us turn to wine, the third beverage under consideration. As shown in Figure 4, the proportion of wine consumers among alcohol consumers is fairly stable in each group. It is worth noting that wine consumption tends to be more prevalent among higher income groups. In groups 4 and 5, for example, wine consumers account for 35–43% of all alcohol consumers, whereas in groups 1 and 2, this figure is 25–32%. These changes in vodka, beer and wine consumption may be due to changes in the age structure of the population, shifts in beverage preferences caused by the emergence of features of 'post-modern society' (Roshchina and Kondratenko 2024), and the impact of anti-alcohol policies.

Based on the review of literature and the descriptive analysis of alcohol consumption patterns among the Russian population in recent years, we put forward the following hypothesis: the price elasticity of demand for the same alcoholic beverage may vary among population groups with different income levels.

Methodology

An econometric analysis was conducted to test the hypothesis. Consumption models for each type of alcohol (vodka, beer, and wine) were evaluated separately. The Heckman model was used, which included respondents who consumed a particular type of alcohol as well as those who did not, in order to avoid bias in the findings. First, a model of a person's choice to 'drink/not drink a particular type of alcohol' was estimated, and then, for those who consumed this type of alcohol, a model of consumption volume was estimated.

It should be noted that the price and demand for alcohol (i.e. consumption volume in this case) may be endogenous variables. In a market economy, price significantly affects purchase and consumption volumes; conversely, what and how much people buy significantly affects pricing. To avoid inconsistencies in the estimates caused by endogeneity, this study employed a two-step approach. This methodology has previously been used in several studies to estimate the price elasticity of alcohol consumption (Yakovlev 2018; Kolosnitsyna and Sukhanova 2023). In these studies, consumer price indices and vodka excise duty were used as instrumental variables, and the actual minimum vodka prices in the places of residence of the respondents were used as a price indicator (Kolosnitsyna and Sukhanova 2023).

In this study, the first stage involved estimating the model (see equation 1), in which the price variable was used as the dependent variable. Next, in Heckman's model (see equations 2.1–2.3), the results estimated from equation 1 were used as the price variable instead of the true values. The Heckman models were estimated using a two-step method involving bootstrapping to restore the standard errors and avoid bias resulting from the use of estimated rather than true price values.

Dependent variables

The dependent variables used in the study include:

price_beverage – actual minimum price per litre of a specific beverage (vodka, beer or wine) in the respondent's place of residence, normalised to the regional average monthly income as a percentage. The study focused on minimum prices, since most respondents to the RLMS survey had low or medium incomes. Normalising this indicator by income reflects the affordability of the beverage in the respondent's region of residence. Normalisation also ensures comparability of indicators across years and regions, as they become dimensionless. Minimum beverage prices in the respondent's place of residence were taken from RLMS data on 'Infrastructure of the settlement. Food Prices' and the average per capita income values in the respondents' regions of residence were taken from Rosstat data;

drink_beverage – binary variable (1: consumed a specific type of beverage (vodka/beer/wine) in the last 30 days; 0: did not consume a specific type of beverage (vodka/beer/wine) in the last 30 days);

ln (beverage) – continuous variable, natural logarithm of the total individual consumption of alcoholic beverages (vodka/beer/wine) in grams per month.

Independent variables

All socio-economic characteristics of respondents and their places of residence were selected as independent control variables based on earlier studies using foreign and RLMS data, which found that these factors impacted the probability and volume of consumption (Baltagi and Geishecker 2006; Roshchina 2012; Roshchina, Martynenko 2014; Kolosnitsyna et al. 2015; Cheah 2015; Collins 2016; Chea 2020; Sadykova 2023).

age – respondent's age (years, last birthday) at the time of the survey;

agesq – respondent's squared age (years, last birthday); this is used because previous studies have shown that people initially consume more alcohol as they age, and then less;

male – binary variable, individual's sex (1: man, 0: woman);

live_place – binary variable, individual's place of residence (0: village or urban-type settlement, 1: city or regional centre, including Moscow and St Petersburg);

ed – categorical variable, individual's education (1: incomplete secondary education, 2: completed secondary education, 3: technical college graduate or incomplete higher education, 4: completed higher education (including academic degree));

relig – categorical variable, individual's level of religious commitment (1: non-believer or atheist, 2: more of non-believer than believer, 3: believer rather than non-believer, 4: religious person);

marry – binary variable, individual's marital status (1: married (registered or not), 0: not married);

work – binary variable, for whether or not the respondent is employed; a person is considered employed if any of the following responses is selected: 'currently working', 'on maternity leave' or 'on paid or unpaid leave' (1: employed, 0: unemployed);

child – binary variable, for whether or not the respondent has minor children (1: has children; 0: does not have children);

ln_income – natural logarithm of average household income (recalculated based on the equivalence scale, roubles per month), indexed to 2011 prices using the consumer price index (CPI) for goods and services in different regions of Russia;

sales_hours – number of hours per day during which the sale of alcohol is permitted in the region.

For the first stage of modelling and estimation of the price indicator, official Rosstat data from 2011 to 2022 was used as follows:

lnipc – natural logarithm of the region's consumer price index;

lic – number of licences issued for the purchase, storage and supply of alcoholic and alcohol-containing products per capita in the respondent's region of residence;

lnexduty_beverage – natural logarithm of the excise duty on various types of alcoholic beverage (in roubles per litre of vodka, beer or wine), calculated in 2011 prices and considering Russia's regional CPIs.

These indicators are used as instrumental variables in addition to the socio-economic characteristics of individuals. The CPI accounts for general price trends in the region (Yakovlev 2018; Kolosnitsyna and Sukhanova 2023). The number of licences issued stands for the level of competition: the more licences issued, the more businesses are eligible to sell alcohol, resulting in higher competition and lower selling prices. The size of the excise duty reflects the government anti-alcohol policy's impact on price changes (Yakovlev 2018). To compare models with fixed and random effects, Hausman tests were conducted on the general sample for each beverage's price indicator. The results suggest that the null hypothesis, which assumes the validity of the random effects model, is not rejected in favour of the fixed effects model (for vodka: p -value = 0.157; for beer: p -value = 0.248; for wine: p -value = 0.079). Accordingly, the preferred option is the model with random individual effects. This is to be expected, given that the RLMS sample comprises randomly selected households.

Stage One (estimating the price of a beverage using instrumental variables) – a panel model with random effects:

$$\begin{aligned} price_beverage_{it} = & \beta_1 \times lnipc_{rt} + \beta_2 \times lic_{rt} + \beta_3 \times \\ & \times lnexduty_{beverage_t} + \beta_4 \times H_{it} + \alpha_i + \mu_{it}, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where i – respondent's index, r – Russian region's index, and l – index of the respondent's place of residence, t – year of observation, H_{it} – socio-economic characteristics of individuals from the set of independent variables, excluding the squared age; α_i – random individual effects, μ_{it} – standard errors.

Stage Two (estimation of beverage consumption) – Heckman’s two-step model:

At this stage, the first step is to estimate the probability of an individual consuming a particular beverage (estimating actual consumption). To achieve this, a probit model with random individual effects was used, in which the beverage price was the value estimated from equation 1.

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(\text{drink}_{\text{beverage}_{it}} = 1) &= P(\text{drink}_{\text{beverage}_{it}}^* > 0) = \\
 &= P(X_{it}\gamma + \tau_1 * \widehat{\text{price}}_{\text{beverage}_{it}} + \varepsilon_{it} > 0) = \Phi(X_{it}\gamma + \tau_1 * \widehat{\text{price}}_{\text{beverage}_{it}}),
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2.1}$$

$$\text{drink}_{\text{beverage}_{it}} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \text{drink}_{\text{beverage}_{it}}^* > 0 \\ 0, & \text{if } \text{drink}_{\text{beverage}_{it}}^* \leq 0 \end{cases}
 \tag{2.2}$$

where i – respondent’s index, l – index of the respondent’s place of residence, X_{it} – socio-economic characteristics of individuals; ε_{it} – random error with a standard normal distribution; Φ – cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution.

The second step is to estimate the consumption volume for those individuals who consume a specific beverage:

$$\ln(\text{beverage}_{it}) = X_{it}\theta + \delta_1 * \widehat{\text{price}}_{\text{beverage}_{it}} + \delta_2 * \text{IMR}_{it} + \varphi_i + \varepsilon_{it},
 \tag{2.3}$$

where X_{it} – socio-economic characteristics of individuals, φ_i – random individual effects; $\widehat{\text{price}}_{\text{beverage}_{it}}$ – estimates obtained from equation (1), IMR_{it} – inverse Mills ratio; ε_{it} – standard errors.

Models (1) and (2.1)–(2.3) were estimated one after the other for each beverage (vodka, beer and wine) across the entire sample and for each income group separately.

Let us take a closer look at the estimation of wine consumption models. Because wine is heterogeneous and has different alcohol content, its price can vary significantly. The descriptive analysis of the data revealed that in each year under review, around 70%⁶ of wine consuming respondents consumed dry wine and/or sparkling wine. Therefore, given the significant dominance of these types of wine, the models were specifically designed for dry and sparkling wine consumption.

Furthermore, the model included dummy variables corresponding to the years of observation to account for unobservable time effects. The data were also tested for autocorrelation, but none was detected.

All calculations were performed using STATA, version 17.

Findings

Using the Heckman model, the study estimated the demand elasticity for alcoholic beverages across the entire sample and in five income groups among the Russian population. This revealed significant differences in consumer preferences and responses to price changes among Russians with different incomes. The full results of the model estimation are presented in Appendix 2, Tables A1–A7. All the model’s coefficient values for variable prices

6 The authors’ calculations show that in 2011, 69.48% of wine consumers drank dry wine or sparkling wine, only 24% drank fortified wine, and 15.26% drank home-made wine. By 2022, the figures had changed, with 70.94% drinking dry wine or sparkling wine, 23.49% drinking fortified wine, and 16.41% drinking home-made wine. These results are consistent with earlier studies by Kondratenko (2021) and Roschina (2012).

are significant and show negative price elasticity of consumption, which is characteristic of normal goods.

The results of the elasticity estimation are presented in Table 2. The overall price elasticities for vodka, beer, and wine across the entire sample were -0.221, -0.299, and -0.789, respectively. As shown in Table 2, the values for the entire sample illustrate the averaged situation. Looking at the results for individual income groups reveals that the least affluent consumers have the lowest absolute elasticity of vodka consumption by price (-0.162). This may be because this income group has the highest proportion of vodka consumers, as well as the highest consumption per consumer⁷, and the lowest substitution with expensive drinks such as brandy or whisky. Members of this group may also be addicted to vodka and, due to their low incomes, may choose the cheapest varieties, meaning a small relative change in price would have little impact on them. This finding confirms our assumption that the poorer population in Russia, who consume the most vodka, will have low price elasticity of demand.

Table 2. Estimates of price elasticities of consumption for different types of alcohol by income group*

Alcoholic beverage	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Entire Sample
Vodka	-0.162	-0.258	-0.206	-0.219	-0.235	-0.221
Beer	-0.284	-0.314	-0.539	-0.412	-0.230	-0.299
Dry and sparkling wine	-1.508	-1.303	-0.723	-0.440	-0.618	-0.789

Source: authors' calculations. Note: * Detailed results of the model estimation are presented in Appendix 2, Tables A1–A7

At the same time, the highest demand elasticity for wine within the same group compared to others indicates that consumers significantly reduce wine consumption when prices rise. The poorest group has the lowest proportion of wine consumers (see Fig. 4), so they are more likely to give up this beverage in favour of others when prices rise. Conversely, the lowest price elasticities of wine consumption are found in groups 4 and 5, which was to be expected given that this beverage is most popular among them and the habit is stronger. Price increases do not cause a significant reduction in wine consumption among these groups, due to their high incomes and sufficient degree of addiction.

The group with an average income had the highest absolute demand elasticity for beer (-0.539), compared to other groups. This suggests that consumers with an average income can more easily adapt to fluctuations in beer prices by choosing different beverages. At the same time, the demand elasticity for beer exhibited inverse U-shaped behaviour in relation to income. The lowest values were found in groups with minimum and maximum income levels (-0.284 and -0.230, respectively), which have the highest and lowest proportions of beer consumers (see Figure 3). This may be because, in groups with an average income, it is easier to switch from beer to wine when beer prices rise, as wine has a lower consumption elasticity than other beverages.

Overall, the findings suggest that if the prices of vodka, beer and wine should increase by the same amount, people on low incomes would significantly reduce their wine consumption while barely giving up vodka. Those on average incomes may give up beer or wine

⁷ According to the authors' calculations, the poorest group had the highest average consumption level of vodka between 2011 and 2022, at 323 grams per month.

first, while the wealthiest would reduce their consumption of dry or sparkling wine, but by a smaller amount.

We would also like to highlight another important finding of the study, that is, the impact of the variable ‘sales hours’ as a non-price instrument of anti-alcohol policy on different income groups. Longer permitted hours in the respondent’s region of residence were found to increase vodka and beer consumption among groups 1–3, and wine consumption among group 1 (see Appendix 2, Table A5–A7). These findings suggest that measures to restrict permitted hours, alongside price increases, are an effective anti-alcohol policy tool. Secondly, this measure impacts low- and middle-income groups because they tend to purchase alcohol in nearby shops as and when required. Restricting permitted hours does indeed reduce the volume of alcohol purchased. Conversely, a night-time sales ban would not significantly impact wealthier individuals, who can afford to consume alcohol in bars and restaurants and may also stock up on alcohol purchased earlier during permitted hours.

Robustness checks

To check how sensitive the results are to limitations in the sample, we estimated the above models again, this time limiting the maximum age of the population under consideration to 72 years (instead of 80). According to the International Labour Organisation’s methodology, which is also adopted by Rosstat, people under 72 years of age are considered to be of working age. The results of this check are presented in Appendix 2, Table A8. It is worth noting that the average indicators for all groups differ by 3–4% for vodka and by 2–3% for beer and wine from those previously obtained for the population up to 80 years of age. No significant differences were found in the control variables. At the same time, the poorest group has the lowest vodka consumption elasticity and the highest wine consumption elasticity. Variations in the elasticity of wine and vodka consumption across groups remain non-monotonic. Therefore, changes in the age limits of the sample do not fundamentally affect the obtained results, indicating their robustness.

Additionally, to verify the robustness of the results across income groups, we constructed and estimated models dividing respondents into four income groups by quartiles (instead of quintiles). The results are presented in Table 3 and Appendix 2, Table A9. The elasticity values for beer remain inversely U-shaped. At the same time, reducing the number of income groups leads to the formation of a U-shaped pattern of elasticities for wine consumption, which may be caused by respondents moving to other income groups under the new classification. However, for the poorest group, consumption elasticity remains the lowest for vodka and the highest for wine, confirming the robustness of the results.

Table 3. Results of estimating price elasticities of consumption of different types of alcohol by income groups (quartiles) for the working-age population

Alcoholic beverage	1st quartile	2nd quartile	3rd quartile	4th quartile
Vodka	-0.196	-0.229	-0.223	-0.273
Beer	-0.243	-0.387	-0.495	-0.230
Dry and sparkling wine	-1.520	-1.173	-0.530	-0.693

Source: compiled by the authors

Conclusion

The study showed that the price elasticity of consumption of different alcoholic beverages (vodka, beer, and wine) varies not only between the beverages, but also between consumers with different income levels. Previous studies of alcohol-related behaviours in Russia provided general estimates of the price elasticity of vodka or total alcohol consumption in different years for the entire Russian population. These values varied depending on the observation period, analytical methods, and data used. Studies based on RLMS data found that the elasticity of total alcohol consumption in grams of pure alcohol relative to the price of vodka ranged from -0.145 to -0.67 in the late 1990s and early 2000s (Andrienko and Nemtsov 2005; Treisman 2010), and from -0.67 to -0.93 between 2011 and 2014 (Kolosnitsyna and Sukhanova 2024). During the COVID-19 pandemic, this indicator was significantly higher, reaching -1.92 for men and -1.8 for women in 2021 (Kondratenko and Zolorareva 2024). The price elasticity of vodka consumption in individual years between 2011 and 2014 ranged from -0.75 to -1.24 (Kolosnitsyna and Sukhanova 2023). In the late 1990s and early 2000s, the price elasticity of consumption for individual beverages ranged from -1.0 for wine, -1.8 for vodka, and -3.0 for beer (Andrienko and Nemtsov 2005). Roschina (2013) noted the insignificance of certain price indicators for beverages and a more significant impact of social factors on alcohol consumption.

Similar to most of the above-mentioned studies, this study obtained significant negative values of price elasticity of alcohol consumption for different types of beverages (e.g. vodka, beer and wine). However, the estimates we obtained differ from earlier findings for Russia. These differences can primarily be explained by our use of a different methodology (two-step Heckman models with instrumental variables combined with normalised alcohol prices). Secondly, the estimates are based on new data. Earlier studies examined periods before anti-alcohol policies were implemented (Andrienko and Nemtsov 2005; Baltagi and Geishecker 2006), or conversely, only considered years with significant excise duty increases, specifically 2011–2014 (Yakovlev 2018; Kolosnitsyna and Sukhanova 2023). In contrast, our results consider alcohol consumption from the inception of active anti-alcohol policies in 2011 until 2022, encompassing the period from 2017 onwards when a clear upward trend in consumption emerged (Kolosnitsyna 2024).

The novelty of this study lies in the fact that, firstly, an attempt was made for the first time to assess the responses of people with different income levels to price changes based on Russian data. Studies conducted abroad had concluded that the responses of people with different income levels to changes in the prices of addictive goods may differ from country to country (Selvaraj et al. 2015; Kumar 2017; Pryce et al. 2019). The low value of the vodka consumption elasticity coefficient obtained in this study for the poorest population group (-0.16) is consistent with earlier studies based on foreign data (Shrestha 2015; Pryce et al. 2019), as well as a study by Goryakin et al. (2015, p.192), who found a weak positive but insignificant response to price increases in population groups with low economic status and termed vodka a Giffen good. Our hypothesis was confirmed; it was indeed found that the response to changes in the prices of vodka, beer and dry wine varied greatly between wealthy and poor consumers. This is apparently due to their incomes, established preferences and the degree of addiction to certain beverages. For example, wealthier people would avoid wine less when its price increases compared with other groups, while the poorest would continue to choose vodka as their 'unalterable' drink of choice.

Secondly, the study also estimated the impact of an important non-pricing instrument of anti-alcohol policy: regulated permitted hours for alcohol sales in the region. A positive correlation was found between the established hours of alcohol sales and the consumption of vodka, beer and wine in some income groups, which is consistent with the results of earlier studies on this topic (Kolosnitsyna et al. 2014). However, this study is the first to estimate consumer response to night-time sales bans by income group. As a result, the finding on the impact of this anti-alcohol policy instrument is refined as follows: night-time alcohol sales bans are more effective for low- and middle-income groups than for higher-income groups.

Based on the results obtained, we can conclude that low-income groups present a particular challenge in terms of pricing policy effectiveness. They are unlikely to respond significantly to further increases in excise duties and prices. Non-pricing measures, particularly restrictions on permitted hours, are likely to be the most effective way of reaching these groups. Therefore, restrictions on the permitted hours for the sale of alcohol should be prioritised in poorer regions with a higher proportion of poor households.

Furthermore, the study identified certain patterns in how individual socio-economic factors impact the consumption of different types of alcohol, such as vodka, beer and wine. Thus, the study confirmed previous findings on the squared effect of age on alcohol consumption and the inverse relationship between vodka and beer consumption and level of education (Roshchina 2013; Kolosnitsyna et al. 2015; Collins 2016; Chea 2020; Khorkina et al. 2022; Eltsov and Khorkina 2023; Sadykova 2023). Conversely, with regard to dry and sparkling wine, it was found that consumption increases with an increase in level of education in all income groups. City dwellers are less likely to consume vodka and do consume less of it, but they consume more beer and wine than rural residents. The presence of children has a greater impact on vodka consumption: low-income households with children would consume less vodka, whereas the likelihood of beer consumption among households with children would increase in low- and middle-income groups. In low-income groups, an increase in income reduces vodka consumption. In above-average income groups, however, an increase in income increases the likelihood and volume of wine consumption. A positive correlation with income was also found for beer consumption in four out of five groups.

This study has several limitations. Firstly, the RLMS sample is biased towards lower incomes, meaning it is not possible to extrapolate the results to the alcohol-related behaviours of the higher-income groups. Secondly, the sample is not representative at the regional level, which means that only conclusions for the Russian population as a whole can be drawn. Thirdly, estimates of alcohol consumption based on survey data are not always reliable, as people may underreport, underestimate or deliberately conceal their consumption. Fourthly, the limitations of the wine consumption models should be noted: they were built only for dry and sparkling wine, and the number of observations there is significantly smaller than for other types of alcoholic beverage, so the results should be interpreted with caution.

Further research should be conducted to consider the possible substitution effects of individual beverages as their prices change, as well as to calculate the cross-elasticity of consumption. Additionally, it would be interesting to estimate the responses to changes in prices of alcoholic beverages among men and women within the same income groups, as these may vary significantly.

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Appendix 1

Box-and-whisker plots for consumption volumes of different beverages

The diagrams were constructed using the methods of Tukey (1977)⁸ and Cleveland (1993)⁹, whereby the lower part of each boxplot represents the 25th percentile and the upper part represents the 75th percentile. The interquartile range is the difference between the 75th and 25th percentiles. The lower whisker below the box is calculated as the 25th percentile minus 1.5 times the interquartile range. The upper whisker above the box is calculated as the 75th percentile plus 1.5 times the interquartile range. Values falling outside the range between the upper and lower whiskers are considered outliers.

Diagram 1: Box and Whisker Plot of Vodka Consumption Volumes

Diagram 2: Box and Whisker Plot of Beer Consumption Volumes

Diagram 3: Box and Whisker Plot of Wine Consumption Volumes

Figure A1. Box-and-whisker plots for consumption volumes of different beverages

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Appendix 2

Table A1. Estimation Results, First Stage. Estimation of Price Indicators. Estimation of the Price Indicator for Vodka

Variables	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Entire Sample
	price_vodka					
lnipc	1.944** (0.940)	4.080*** (0.901)	3.794*** (0.789)	1.793** (0.751)	1.629** (0.647)	3.018*** (0.325)
lic	-36.77*** (1.573)	-32.68*** (1.735)	-34.96*** (1.536)	-32.86*** (1.337)	-30.55*** (1.304)	-28.85*** (0.753)
lnexduty_vodka	0.615* (0.324)	0.129* (0.094)	0.138** (0.065)	0.492** (0.227)	0.267* (0.127)	0.267** (0.108)
Individual's socio-economic characteristics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Dummy variables corresponding to the year of observation	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Constant	-11.25*** (3.066)	-19.77*** (3.096)	-14.96*** (2.782)	-11.67*** (2.637)	-7.070*** (2.159)	-13.81*** (1.102)
Observations	4.059	4.337	4.737	5.014	5.375	23.522
Number of individuals	2.587	2.861	3.11	3.182	3.104	9.067
R ²	0.2802	0.3493	0.3699	0.3093	0.3648	0.3187
sigma_u	0.3123	0.3083	0.3181	0.2986	0.2747	0.2859
sigma_e	0.3401	0.3319	0.3114	0.2858	0.2664	0.3136
Rho	0.4575	0.4636	0.5108	0.5217	0.5153	0.4541

Notes: Robust standard errors are indicated in parentheses. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Table A2. Estimation of the Price Indicator for Beer

Variables	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Entire Sample
	price_beer					
lnipc	0.349*** (0.0784)	0.0979 (0.0855)	0.122 (0.0857)	0.233*** (0.0875)	0.586*** (0.0749)	0.402*** (0.0332)
lic	-7.373*** (0.165)	-6.972*** (0.150)	-7.780*** (0.144)	-8.044*** (0.139)	-7.841*** (0.143)	-7.294*** (0.0726)
lnexduty_beer	0.144*** (0.0334)	0.204*** (0.0324)	0.205*** (0.0321)	0.0984*** (0.0322)	0.183*** (0.0296)	0.115*** (0.0154)
Individual's socio-economic characteristics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Dummy variables corresponding to the year of observation	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Variables	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Entire Sample
	price_beer					
Constant	1.905*** (0.408)	0.705 (0.441)	0.940** (0.436)	1.430*** (0.445)	2.917*** (0.378)	2.198*** (0.174)
Observations	5.648	5.721	6.369	6.931	6.801	31470
Number of individuals	3.365	3.657	4.097	4.323	4.288	11.547
R ²	0.3052	0.2952	0.2729	0.3030	0.3770	0.3875
sigma_u	0.0543	0.0597	0.0593	0.0627	0.0656	0.0532
sigma_e	0.0894	0.0830	0.0826	0.0773	0.0652	0.0812
rho	0.2693	0.3427	0.3401	0.3971	0.5032	0.3006

Notes: Robust standard errors are indicated in parentheses. ****p* < 0.01, ***p* < 0.05, **p* < 0.1

Table A3. Estimation of the Price Indicator for Dry Wine, Sparkling Wine

Variables	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Entire Sample
	price_wine					
lnipc	4.522*** (0.875)	4.528*** (0.885)	4.297*** (0.794)	5.737*** (0.698)	7.349*** (0.539)	3.596*** (0.125)
lic	-21.87*** (1.363)	-26.96*** (1.308)	-25.92*** (1.179)	-24.62*** (1.026)	-22.08*** (0.901)	-22.60*** (0.245)
lnexduty_wine	1.617*** (0.301)	1.725*** (0.272)	1.276*** (0.257)	2.085*** (0.235)	2.525*** (0.202)	0.654*** (0.0584)
Individual's socio-economic characteristics	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Dummy variables corresponding to the year of observation	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Constant	-23.09*** (4.261)	-23.21*** (4.357)	-20.38*** (3.874)	-29.35*** (3.420)	-36.55*** (2.602)	-16.60*** (0.617)
Observations	2.976	3.079	3.727	4.576	5.268	19.696
Number of individuals	1.974	2.282	2.706	3.129	3.738	7.809
R ²	0.2196	0.2048	0.2504	0.2563	0.3101	0.3073
sigma_u	0.1608	0.1951	0.1745	0.1697	0.1814	0.1701
sigma_e	0.2894	0.2849	0.2817	0.2809	0.2393	0.2950
rho	0.2361	0.3192	0.2774	0.2773	0.3651	0.2496

Notes: Robust standard errors are indicated in parentheses. ****p* < 0.01, ***p* < 0.05, **p* < 0.1. sig-

ma_u – standard error for u effects, sigma_e – standard error for e,
$$\rho = \frac{(\sigma_u)^2}{(\sigma_u)^2 + (\sigma_e)^2}$$

Table A4. Heckman model estimations for the probability and volume of consumption of vodka, beer, dry wine and sparkling wine

Variables	Probability of vodka consumption	Volume of vodka consumption	Probability of beer consumption	Volume of beer consumption	Probability of dry wine consumption	Volume of dry wine consumption
Price indicator	0.132 (0.972)	-0.221*** (0.0500)	0.0866 (0.0875)	-0.299*** (0.0574)	-1.157*** (0.0778)	-0.789*** (0.218)
Sex (male)	1.146*** (0.0247)	1.260*** (0.100)	0.939*** (0.0275)	0.830*** (0.0243)	-1.418*** (0.0245)	-0.457 (0.280)
Age (age)	0.123*** (0.00511)	0.116*** (0.0111)	-0.0358*** (0.00567)	0.0415*** (0.00381)	-0.0316*** (0.00474)	0.0234*** (0.00724)
Squared age (agesq)	-0.00101*** (5.36e-05)	-0.00113*** (9.51e-05)	-8.15e-05 (6.03e-05)	-0.000554*** (4.27e-05)	0.000275*** (5.06e-05)	-0.000381*** (6.69e-05)
Education (ed) (base category: 1 – incomplete secondary education)						
completed secondary	-0.0701** (0.0303)	-0.108*** (0.0255)	-0.152*** (0.0355)	-0.0605*** (0.0222)	0.176*** (0.0362)	0.0609 (0.0539)
completed technical college or incomplete higher	-0.187*** (0.0341)	-0.255*** (0.0315)	-0.253*** (0.0390)	-0.182*** (0.0241)	0.435*** (0.0371)	0.139 (0.0953)
completed higher (including postgrad degree)	-0.507*** (0.0356)	-0.476*** (0.0531)	-0.449*** (0.0399)	-0.294*** (0.0278)	0.817*** (0.0375)	0.333** (0.158)
Marital status (marry)	0.0142 (0.0247)	-0.0353** (0.0179)	0.0635** (0.0271)	-0.0409** (0.0166)	-0.0129 (0.0228)	0.00329 (0.0198)
Level of religious commitment (relig) (base category: 1 – non-believer or atheist)						
more of non-believer than believer	0.0273 (0.0323)	-0.0323 (0.0238)	0.0416 (0.0361)	-0.0628*** (0.0236)	0.00504 (0.0377)	-0.102*** (0.0392)
believer rather than non-believer	-0.0525* (0.0301)	-0.142*** (0.0225)	-0.00939 (0.0340)	-0.104*** (0.0214)	0.0677** (0.0336)	-0.0712** (0.0349)
religious person	-0.0678** (0.0327)	-0.141*** (0.0269)	-0.112*** (0.0366)	-0.0931*** (0.0245)	0.0825** (0.0356)	-0.0394 (0.0365)

Variables	Probability of vodka consumption	Volume of vodka consumption	Probability of beer consumption	Volume of beer consumption	Probability of dry wine consumption	Volume of dry wine consumption
Being employed (work)	-0.00736 (0.0234)	-0.100*** (0.0170)	0.0673*** (0.0254)	0.0102 (0.0183)	0.107*** (0.0239)	0.0732*** (0.0268)
Natural logarithm of average per capita household income (ln_income)	-0.0388** (0.0165)	-0.0354*** (0.0132)	-0.00143 (0.0179)	0.0316*** (0.0105)	0.165*** (0.0170)	0.166*** (0.0316)
Presence of children (child)	0.0325 (0.0315)	-0.0687*** (0.0238)	0.163*** (0.0342)	0.0228 (0.0213)	-0.0662** (0.0301)	-0.0242 (0.0299)
Place of residence (live_place)	-0.0574** (0.0274)	-0.0514** (0.0214)	0.138*** (0.0304)	0.162*** (0.0200)	0.214*** (0.0257)	0.242*** (0.0457)
Permitted hours for alcohol sales in the region of residence (sales_hours)	-0.0201 (0.0632)	0.0180*** (0.00460)	0.0183*** (0.00707)	0.0150*** (0.00499)	0.00886 (0.00626)	0.000357 (0.00510)
IMR		0.533*** (0.126)		0.0199 (0.0385)		0.638** (0.256)
Dummy variables corresponding to the year of observation	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Constant	-2.989*** (0.234)	3.478*** (0.405)	4.055*** (0.255)	6.008*** (0.132)	-0.891*** (0.224)	3.664*** (0.401)
Observations	64.150	23.522	59.238	31470	65.017	19.696
Number of individuals	17.760	9.067	16.864	11.547	17.457	7.809

Notes: Standard bootstrapped errors are shown in parentheses *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Table A5. Heckman model estimations for the probability and volume of vodka consumption by income groups

Variables	Group 1		Group 2		Group 3		Group 4		Group 5	
	Probability of vodka consumption	Volume of vodka consumption	Probability of vodka consumption	Volume of vodka consumption	Probability of vodka consumption	Volume of vodka consumption	Probability of vodka consumption	Volume of vodka consumption	Probability of vodka consumption	Volume of vodka consumption
Price indicator (price_vodka)	0.0291 (0.110)	-0.162** (0.0861)	0.0996* (0.033)	-0.258*** (0.0989)	0.229** (0.115)	-0.206*** (0.0829)	0.1214** (0.0854)	-0.219*** (0.0804)	0.358*** (0.113)	-0.235*** (0.0843)
Sex (male)	1.020*** (0.0487)	1.004*** (0.215)	1.098*** (0.0521)	1.263*** (0.169)	1.154*** (0.0493)	1.091*** (0.169)	1.291*** (0.0513)	1.150*** (0.153)	1.242*** (0.0477)	1.097*** (0.148)
Age (age)	0.128*** (0.0102)	0.113*** (0.0271)	0.138*** (0.0104)	0.130*** (0.0225)	0.134*** (0.0102)	0.101*** (0.0200)	0.147*** (0.0106)	0.0987*** (0.0184)	0.128*** (0.0103)	0.0901*** (0.0133)
Squared age (agesq)	-0.00111*** (0.000108)	-0.00114*** (0.000239)	-0.00113*** (0.000106)	-0.00125*** (0.000190)	-0.00109*** (0.000106)	-0.000960*** (0.000171)	-0.00123*** (0.000110)	-0.000952*** (0.000160)	-0.00107*** (0.000109)	-0.000917*** (0.000118)
<i>Education (ed) (base category: 1 – incomplete secondary education)</i>										
completed secondary	-0.132** (0.0556)	-0.0904* (0.0491)	-0.111* (0.0605)	-0.0685 (0.0464)	-0.0268 (0.0644)	-0.0420 (0.0444)	-0.0654 (0.0702)	-0.0961** (0.0445)	-0.0964 (0.0706)	-0.0887* (0.0531)
completed technical college or incomplete higher	-0.258*** (0.0649)	-0.172** (0.0764)	-0.213*** (0.0670)	-0.211*** (0.0544)	-0.223*** (0.0671)	-0.211*** (0.0578)	-0.202*** (0.0729)	-0.230*** (0.0496)	-0.223*** (0.0744)	-0.222*** (0.0543)
completed higher (including post-grad degree)	-0.456*** (0.0715)	-0.322*** (0.111)	-0.489*** (0.0721)	-0.501*** (0.0962)	-0.519*** (0.0702)	-0.384*** (0.0942)	-0.553*** (0.0728)	-0.363*** (0.0783)	-0.619*** (0.0730)	-0.419*** (0.0880)
Marital status (marry)	0.0312 (0.0513)	-0.0292 (0.0382)	-0.00822 (0.0523)	-0.0437 (0.0417)	0.0327 (0.0504)	-0.0387 (0.0376)	0.00986 (0.0514)	-0.0352 (0.0381)	0.0728 (0.0454)	0.0209 (0.0367)

Variables	Group 1		Group 2		Group 3		Group 4		Group 5	
	Probability of vodka consumption	Volume of vodka consumption	Probability of vodka consumption	Volume of vodka consumption	Probability of vodka consumption	Volume of vodka consumption	Probability of vodka consumption	Volume of vodka consumption	Probability of vodka consumption	Volume of vodka consumption
<i>Level of religious commitment (relig) (base category: 1 – non-believer or atheist)</i>										
more of non-believer than believer	-0.00705 (0.0707)	-0.0403 (0.0554)	-0.0580 (0.0771)	-0.0506 (0.0465)	0.0840 (0.0773)	-0.0141 (0.0502)	0.0820 (0.0761)	0.0259 (0.0503)	0.0798 (0.0684)	-0.0289 (0.0462)
believer rather than non-believer	-0.0989 (0.0656)	-0.174*** (0.0490)	-0.116* (0.0694)	-0.211*** (0.0443)	-0.0391 (0.0685)	-0.104** (0.0463)	-0.00203 (0.0667)	-0.0518 (0.0418)	0.0684 (0.0605)	-0.0987** (0.0468)
religious person	-0.122* (0.0718)	-0.206*** (0.0608)	-0.136* (0.0749)	-0.215*** (0.0494)	-0.0724 (0.0734)	-0.123** (0.0562)	-0.0350 (0.0724)	-0.0288 (0.0508)	-0.0176 (0.0651)	-0.127*** (0.0470)
Being employed (work)	-0.148*** (0.0464)	-0.207*** (0.0483)	0.0188 (0.0517)	-0.112*** (0.0362)	0.0663 (0.0526)	-0.0183 (0.0439)	-0.0147 (0.0527)	-0.142*** (0.0355)	-0.183*** (0.0515)	-0.135*** (0.0423)
Natural logarithm of average per capita household income (ln_income)	-0.0764 (0.0574)	-0.0926* (0.0479)	0.410** (0.206)	-0.0776* (0.0358)	-0.356 (0.222)	0.0293 (0.154)	0.168 (0.201)	0.212* (0.125)	0.0786 (0.0723)	0.0492 (0.0631)
Presence of children (child)	0.0707 (0.0637)	-0.0935** (0.0476)	-0.0602 (0.0702)	-0.0712** (0.0298)	-0.0887 (0.0636)	-0.0461 (0.0477)	0.0827 (0.0640)	-0.0292 (0.0422)	0.0583 (0.0571)	0.0168 (0.0436)
Place of residence (live_place)	-0.280*** (0.0483)	-0.277*** (0.0389)	-0.0634* (0.0315)	-0.0435** (0.0125)	-0.0426** (0.0194)	-0.0370* (0.0144)	-0.202*** (0.0532)	-0.0634 (0.0428)	-0.0978* (0.0546)	-0.0623* (0.0333)

Variables	Group 1		Group 2		Group 3		Group 4		Group 5	
	Probability of vodka consumption	Volume of vodka consumption	Probability of vodka consumption	Volume of vodka consumption	Probability of vodka consumption	Volume of vodka consumption	Probability of vodka consumption	Volume of vodka consumption	Probability of vodka consumption	Volume of vodka consumption
Permitted hours for alcohol sales in the region of residence (sales_hours)	-0.0180 (0.0120)	0.0361*** (0.00907)	0.0182 (0.0127)	0.139*** (0.0104)	0.00402 (0.0120)	0.0976** (0.00928)	0.0289 (0.125)	-0.0116 (0.00933)	-0.0173 (0.0128)	0.0164 (0.903)
IMR		0.463 (0.309)		0.680*** (0.236)		0.452** (0.208)		0.407** (0.175)		0.360** (0.163)
Dummy variables corresponding to the year of observation	Yes	Yes								
Constant	-2.433*** (0.549)	4.766*** (0.845)	-7.377*** (1.904)	3.289* (1.902)	-0.808 (2.117)	2.819** (1.313)	-5.252*** (1.958)	1.318 (1.356)	-4.423*** (0.812)	3.352*** (0.873)
Observations	10.367	4.059	11.291	4.337	12.298	4.737	13.716	5.014	16.478	5.375
Number of individuals	5.345	2.587	6.453	2.861	7.122	3.11	7.482	3.182	7.454	3.104

Notes: Standard bootstrapped errors are shown in parentheses *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Table A6. Heckman model estimations for the probability and volume of beer consumption by income groups

Variables	Group 1		Group 2		Group 3		Group 4		Group 5	
	Probabil- ity of beer consump- tion	Volume of beer con- sumption								
Price indicator (price_beer)	-0.220 (0.202)	-0.287*** (0.110)	-0.432** (0.204)	-0.314*** (0.116)	0.0438 (0.205)	-0.539*** (0.115)	-0.607*** (0.195)	-0.412*** (0.114)	-0.595*** (0.187)	-0.230* (0.124)
Sex (male)	0.698*** (0.0590)	0.783*** (0.0436)	0.889*** (0.0575)	0.740*** (0.0469)	1.051*** (0.0586)	0.742*** (0.0547)	0.972*** (0.0502)	0.716*** (0.0505)	1.033*** (0.0485)	0.758*** (0.0513)
Age (age)	-0.0411*** (0.0123)	0.0437*** (0.00788)	-0.0458*** (0.0117)	0.0368*** (0.00699)	-0.0528*** (0.0120)	0.0257*** (0.00703)	-0.0494*** (0.0107)	0.0395*** (0.00736)	-0.0270*** (0.0109)	0.0431*** (0.00672)
squared age (agesq)	-7.81e-05 (0.000133)	-0.000608*** (9.61e-05)	-3.62e-05 (0.000122)	-0.000486*** (7.76e-05)	5.52e-05 (0.000125)	-0.000376*** (7.81e-05)	6.83e-05 (0.000113)	-0.000504*** (8.16e-05)	-0.000164 (0.000117)	-0.000580*** (8.08e-05)
<i>Education (ed) (base category: 1 – incomplete secondary education)</i>										
completed sec- ondary	-0.209*** (0.0716)	-0.0191 (0.0353)	-0.150** (0.0721)	0.0453 (0.0424)	-0.198** (0.0774)	-0.111*** (0.0372)	-0.145** (0.0735)	-0.0954** (0.0460)	-0.186** (0.0822)	-0.175*** (0.0485)
completed technical college or incomplete higher	-0.287*** (0.0802)	-0.188*** (0.0484)	-0.278*** (0.0784)	-0.0504 (0.0442)	-0.277*** (0.0823)	-0.193*** (0.0412)	-0.228*** (0.0759)	-0.239*** (0.0472)	-0.334*** (0.0842)	-0.260*** (0.0463)
completed high- er (including postgrad degree)	-0.616*** (0.0878)	-0.294*** (0.0574)	-0.546*** (0.0825)	-0.163*** (0.0492)	-0.430*** (0.0831)	-0.268*** (0.0479)	-0.423*** (0.0755)	-0.307*** (0.0467)	-0.521*** (0.0821)	-0.381*** (0.0494)
Marital status (marry)	-0.0821 (0.0619)	-0.0959** (0.0409)	0.0287 (0.0604)	-0.0898** (0.0349)	0.0983 (0.0603)	-0.00241 (0.0313)	0.0454 (0.0534)	-0.0320 (0.0311)	0.0504 (0.0483)	0.0416 (0.0296)

Variables	Group 1		Group 2		Group 3		Group 4		Group 5	
	Probabil- ity of beer consump- tion	Volume of beer con- sumption								
<i>Level of religious commitment (relig) (base category: I – non-believer or atheist)</i>										
more of non-be- liever than believer	0.0901 (0.0906)	0.00658 (0.0513)	0.0817 (0.0923)	-0.0567 (0.0525)	0.0950 (0.0887)	-0.0645 (0.0481)	0.00849 (0.0806)	0.0538 (0.0472)	0.0456 (0.0705)	-0.140*** (0.0415)
believer rather than non-be- liever	-0.0461 (0.0853)	-0.100* (0.0524)	0.00493 (0.0842)	-0.118** (0.0496)	0.0605 (0.0787)	-0.142*** (0.0510)	-0.0633 (0.0711)	-0.0394 (0.0400)	-0.0754 (0.0629)	-0.121*** (0.0336)
religious person	-0.0657 (0.0905)	-0.0834 (0.0557)	-0.129 (0.0908)	-0.134*** (0.0514)	-0.0776 (0.0848)	-0.134** (0.0522)	-0.194** (0.0768)	-0.00154 (0.0469)	-0.234*** (0.0680)	-0.105*** (0.0386)
Being employed (work)	0.0937 (0.0570)	-0.0351 (0.0389)	0.0466 (0.0577)	0.00625 (0.0316)	0.117* (0.0609)	0.000515 (0.0347)	0.0752 (0.0552)	0.0604* (0.0341)	0.104* (0.0539)	0.0373 (0.0345)
Natural loga- rithm of average per capita house- hold income (ln_income)	0.103 (0.0679)	0.0672* (0.0345)	-0.0172 (0.229)	0.222* (0.128)	0.488 (0.365)	0.247* (0.144)	-0.0566 (0.210)	0.0352 (0.122)	0.0266 (0.0788)	0.116** (0.0518)
Presence of chil- dren (child)	0.315*** (0.0760)	-0.0259 (0.0489)	0.173** (0.0774)	0.0355 (0.0449)	0.258*** (0.0762)	0.0958** (0.0400)	0.158** (0.0655)	0.0389 (0.0376)	0.0964 (0.0593)	0.0384 (0.0313)
Place of residence (live_place)	0.0505 (0.0572)	0.213*** (0.0330)	0.137** (0.0556)	0.141*** (0.0321)	0.115** (0.0584)	0.136*** (0.0305)	0.191*** (0.0553)	0.127*** (0.0385)	0.0735 (0.0593)	0.109*** (0.0344)

Variables	Group 1		Group 2		Group 3		Group 4		Group 5	
	Probabil- ity of beer consump- tion	Volume of beer con- sumption								
Permitted hours for alcohol sales in the region	0.0320** (0.0151)	0.0188* (0.00964)	-0.0194 (0.0144)	0.0121* (0.00722)	0.0308** (0.0143)	0.0158* (0.00819)	0.0108 (0.0130)	0.00630 (0.00805)	0.0322** (0.0131)	0.0164 (0.0880)
(sales_hours)										
IMR		0.231** (0.106)		-0.0319 (0.0793)		-0.0131 (0.0878)		-0.0527 (0.0781)		-0.0399 (0.0784)
Dummy vari- ables corre- sponding to the year of observa- tion	Yes	Yes								
Constant	3.907*** (0.716)	5.722*** (0.355)	5.014** (2.152)	4.453*** (1.181)	0.473 (2.522)	4.324*** (1.345)	4.552** (2.071)	6.163*** (1.212)	4.439*** (0.891)	5.179*** (0.536)
Observations	10.191	5.648	10.399	5.721	11.189	6.369	12.487	6.931	14.972	6.801
Number of indi- viduals	5.459	3.365	6.032	3.657	6.583	4.097	6.92	4.323	6.945	4.288

Notes: Standard bootstrapped errors are shown in parentheses *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Table A7. Heckman model estimations for the probability and volume of dry wine and sparkling wine consumption by income groups

Variables	Group 1		Group 2		Group 3		Group 4		Group 5	
	Probability of wine consumption	Volume of wine consumption	Probability of wine consumption	Volume of wine consumption	Probability of wine consumption	Volume of wine consumption	Probability of wine consumption	Volume of wine consumption	Probability of wine consumption	Volume of wine consumption
Price indicator (price_wine)	-0.0405 (0.711)	-1.508*** (0.178)	-0.692*** (0.149)	-1.303*** (0.357)	-0.959*** (0.154)	-0.723* (0.393)	-1.035*** (0.126)	-0.440** (0.154)	-1.033*** (0.110)	-0.618** (0.294)
Sex (male)	0.513 (0.740)	-1.438*** (0.0658)	-1.462*** (0.0641)	-1.686** (0.758)	-1.579*** (0.0616)	-0.507 (0.704)	-1.449*** (0.0503)	-0.332 (0.522)	-1.332*** (0.0413)	-0.508 (0.376)
Age (age)	-0.0455*** (0.0109)	0.0464* (0.0260)	-0.0365*** (0.0105)	-0.0109 (0.0206)	-0.0227** (0.0104)	0.0202 (0.0136)	-0.0379*** (0.00937)	0.0273* (0.0141)	-0.0247*** (0.00872)	0.0204** (0.00988)
squared age (agesq)	0.000474*** (0.000119)	-0.000597** (0.000278)	0.000311*** (0.000110)	-8.23e-05 (0.000185)	0.000155 (0.000110)	-0.000370*** (0.000120)	0.000354*** (9.99e-05)	-0.000422*** (0.000135)	0.000197** (9.43e-05)	-0.000349*** (9.57e-05)
<i>Education (ed) (base category: 1 – incomplete secondary education)</i>										
completed secondary	0.208*** (0.0787)	-0.0969 (0.126)	0.208*** (0.0769)	0.164 (0.135)	0.123 (0.0806)	0.107 (0.0820)	0.207*** (0.0767)	0.0760 (0.128)	0.209*** (0.0719)	-0.0574 (0.0905)
completed technical college or incomplete	0.564*** (0.0806)	-0.0951 (0.280)	0.559*** (0.0790)	0.522* (0.295)	0.481*** (0.0810)	0.241 (0.210)	0.413*** (0.0768)	0.120 (0.173)	0.435*** (0.0725)	-0.00942 (0.143)
completed higher	0.901*** (0.0858)	-0.168 (0.421)	0.994*** (0.0827)	1.070** (0.485)	0.908*** (0.0826)	0.462 (0.370)	0.850*** (0.0766)	0.249 (0.310)	0.818*** (0.0708)	0.224 (0.236)

Variables	Group 1		Group 2		Group 3		Group 4		Group 5	
	Probability of wine consumption	Volume of wine consumption	Probability of wine consumption	Volume of wine consumption	Probability of wine consumption	Volume of wine consumption	Probability of wine consumption	Volume of wine consumption	Probability of wine consumption	Volume of wine consumption
Marital status (marry)	-0.0417 (0.0547)	0.0367 (0.0447)	-0.0294 (0.0524)	-0.0167 (0.0379)	-0.0584 (0.0516)	-0.0284 (0.0461)	-0.0129 (0.0452)	0.00397 (0.0341)	-0.0154 (0.0377)	-0.00465 (0.0318)
more of non-believer than believer	-0.0842 (0.103)	-0.0273 (0.113)	-0.0833 (0.0992)	-0.248** (0.111)	0.135 (0.102)	-0.146 (0.123)	0.0373 (0.0798)	0.000381 (0.0666)	0.00516 (0.0673)	-0.0372 (0.0666)
believer rather than non-believer	0.0405 (0.0880)	-0.0461 (0.106)	0.0442 (0.0858)	-0.00172 (0.0863)	0.256*** (0.0869)	-0.145 (0.139)	0.105 (0.0704)	0.0124 (0.0679)	0.0764 (0.0579)	0.0195 (0.0624)
religious person	0.0337 (0.0928)	-0.0365 (0.106)	0.0810 (0.0903)	0.0289 (0.0946)	0.177* (0.0914)	-0.104 (0.119)	0.0363 (0.0745)	0.0110 (0.0702)	0.107* (0.0611)	0.0319 (0.0686)
Being employed (work)	0.281*** (0.0576)	-0.00658 (0.150)	0.0763 (0.0556)	0.0977* (0.0541)	-0.0252 (0.0561)	-0.0193 (0.0483)	0.176*** (0.0519)	0.0782 (0.0656)	0.116** (0.0465)	0.0865* (0.0446)
Natural logarithm of average per capita household income (ln_income)	0.0123 (0.0648)	0.0706 (0.0541)	-0.203 (0.228)	-0.0670 (0.223)	0.595** (0.254)	0.946*** (0.318)	0.370* (0.200)	0.586*** (0.198)	0.220*** (0.0663)	0.283*** (0.0740)
Presence of children (child)	-0.113 (0.0709)	-0.0692 (0.0771)	-0.0951 (0.0703)	-0.106 (0.0685)	-0.119* (0.0695)	0.0277 (0.0724)	0.00668 (0.0585)	0.0198 (0.0538)	0.000402 (0.0494)	0.0564 (0.0376)

Level of religious commitment (relig) (base category: 1 – non-believer or atheist)

Variables	Group 1		Group 2		Group 3		Group 4		Group 5	
	Probability of wine consumption	Volume of wine consumption	Probability of wine consumption	Volume of wine consumption	Probability of wine consumption	Volume of wine consumption	Probability of wine consumption	Volume of wine consumption	Probability of wine consumption	Volume of wine consumption
Place of residence (live_place)	0.280*** (0.0534)	0.158 (0.151)	0.272*** (0.0519)	0.466*** (0.137)	0.284*** (0.0541)	0.210* (0.119)	0.199*** (0.0489)	0.226*** (0.0733)	0.147*** (0.0473)	0.170*** (0.0497)
Permitted hours for alcohol sales in the region of residence (sales_hours)	-0.00371 (0.0140)	0.0125* (0.0065)	0.0124 (0.0134)	0.0909 (0.0730)	0.00637 (0.0133)	-0.0216 (0.0108)	-0.0179 (0.0118)	-0.00318 (0.0113)	0.00938 (0.0112)	0.00730 (0.00934)
IMR		-0.224 (0.626)		1.553** (0.633)		0.537 (0.557)		0.469 (0.466)		0.690* (0.390)
Dummy variables corresponding to the year of observation	Yes	Yes								
Constant	0.791 (0.611)	4.516*** (0.558)	2.107 (2.111)	5.694*** (1.907)	-5.369*** (2.431)	-3.312 (3.228)	-2.554 (1.947)	-0.578 (1.943)	-1.606** (0.731)	2.323** (0.905)
Observations	11.126	2.976	11.389	3.079	12.300	3.727	13.766	4.576	16.436	5.268
Number of individuals	5.792	1.974	6.485	2.282	7.124	2.706	7.501	3.129	7.457	3.738

Notes: Standard bootstrapped errors are shown in parentheses *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Table A8. Heckman model estimations for the probability and volume of consumption of vodka, beer, and dry wine / sparkling wine by income groups for the working-age population (up to 72 years old)

Variables	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5
<i>Volume of vodka consumption</i>					
Price indicator (price_vodka)	-0.123*** (0.0358)	-0.230** (0.0936)	-0.177* (0.100)	-0.231** (0.0899)	-0.257** (0.104)
Permitted hours for alcohol sales in the region of residence (sales_hours)	0.0323*** (0.0117)	0.0167* (0.00907)	0.00608 (0.0122)	-0.0114 (0.00859)	-0.0120 (0.00912)
Control variables	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Dummy variables corresponding to the year of observation	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Constant	4.202*** (0.971)	3.704* (2.033)	2.549* (1.516)	1.530* (0.957)	3.191*** (0.949)
Observations	3.789	4.211	4.678	4.895	5.182
Number of individuals	2.436	2.762	3.086	3.154	3.015
<i>Volume of beer consumption</i>					
Price indicator (price_beer)	-0.279** (0.111)	-0.344*** (0.126)	-0.540*** (0.103)	-0.433*** (0.125)	-0.206* (0.117)
Permitted hours for alcohol sales in the region of residence (sales_hours)	0.0210** (0.00925)	0.0132* (0.00750)	0.0151 (0.00921)	0.00730 (0.00826)	0.0158* (0.00896)
Control variables	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Dummy variables corresponding to the year of observation	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Constant	5.799*** (0.408)	4.454*** (1.310)	4.399*** (1.323)	6.419*** (1.298)	5.110*** (0.576)
Observations	5.378	5.211	6.027	6.744	6.578
Number of individuals	3.065	3.372	3.925	4.260	4.152
<i>Volume of dry wine / sparkling wine consumption</i>					
Price indicator (price_wine)	-1.401*** (0.323)	-1.216*** (0.0542)	-0.947** (0.448)	-0.406** (0.139)	-0.694** (0.295)
Permitted hours for alcohol sales in the region of residence (sales_hours)	0.00883 (0.0126)	-0.000325 (0.0146)	-0.0227 (0.123)	-0.000283 (0.0119)	0.0106 (0.00900)
Control variables	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Dummy variables corresponding to the year of observation	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Constant	4.438*** (0.479)	7.208*** (2.107)	-2.941 (2.923)	0.0372 (1.962)	1.687*** (0.026)
Observations	2.143	2.464	2.806	3.367	4.972
Number of individuals	1.402	1.975	2.259	2.763	3.375

Table A9. Heckman model estimations for the probability and volume of consumption of vodka, beer, and dry wine / sparkling wine by income groups (quartiles) for the working-age population (up to 72 years old)

Variables	1st quartile	2nd quartile	3rd quartile	4th quartile
<i>Volume of vodka consumption</i>				
Price indicator (price_vodka)	-0.196*** (0.0764)	-0.229*** (0.0873)	-0.223*** (0.0825)	-0.273*** (0.0968)
Permitted hours for alcohol sales in the region of residence (sales_hours)	0.0217** (0.00925)	0.0157* (0.00893)	-0.00813 (0.00834)	0.0116 (0.00844)
Control variables	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Dummy variables corresponding to the year of observation	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Constant	3.975*** (0.783)	2.868* (1.567)	0.495 (1.370)	3.415*** (0.867)
Observations	5.147	5.580	5.908	6.120
Number of individuals	3.207	3.376	3.770	3.645
<i>Volume of beer consumption</i>				
Price indicator (price_beer)	-0.243** (0.111)	-0.387*** (0.118)	-0.495*** (0.0902)	-0.230** (0.102)
Permitted hours for alcohol sales in the region of residence (sales_hours)	0.0229*** (0.00797)	0.0204*** (0.00731)	0.0106 (0.00691)	0.0142 (0.0722)
Control variables	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Dummy variables corresponding to the year of observation	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Constant	5.929*** (0.317)	6.392*** (0.871)	7.614*** (1.087)	5.591*** (0.510)
Observations	7.054	7.126	7.280	8.478
Number of individuals	3.721	4.432	4.080	4.996
<i>Volume of dry wine / sparkling wine consumption</i>				
Price indicator (price_wine)	-1.520*** (0.332)	-1.173*** (0.332)	-0.530* (0.198)	-0.693** (0.311)
Permitted hours for alcohol sales in the region of residence (sales_hours)	0.0132 (0.0102)	-0.00518 (0.0118)	-0.00504 (0.0109)	0.00882 (0.00810)
Control variables	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Dummy variables corresponding to the year of observation	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Constant	5.081*** (0.509)	2.506* (1.510)	3.742* (2.079)	2.418*** (0.907)
Observations	2.211	3.833	3.966	5.742
Number of individuals	1.540	2.138	2.951	3.953